

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

The importance of publishing in journals that are not yet indexed in Scopus, PubMed or WOS

Carlos Navarro Venegas *

Faculty of Veterinary and Livestock Sciences (FAVET), University of Chile, Santiago, Chile.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2022, 14(03), 629–633

Publication history: Received on 23 May 2022; revised on 25 June 2022; accepted on 27 June 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2022.14.3.0647>

Abstract

Journals indexed in SCOPUS, PUBMED or WOS have had supremacy since long ago. Publishing in them has a sudden importance and with brush strokes of immortality. Not doing it in them sounds like mediocrity. However, no one is born knowing and today there are many other journals indexed to other search engines or not inconsiderable Internet media and that over time will amaze us like a third world war that has already begun. The impact indices will be attributed to "new" journals, which have had high visibility over the years, through -for example- the internet.

Keywords: Research; Journals; Works; Index; Doi; Rankings

1. Introduction

A Biochemist in a Faculty of Veterinary Sciences will always be a contribution to the university community. However, for all it is an exemplary condition to publish under the designs of God, understanding as such the Academic Evaluation Commissions of University, if the mortal intends to climb in his Academic Career. It is not the same, paraphrasing Alejandro Sanz. It is not the same where valid experiences are published or not. Publishing work in top journals (SCOPUS, PUBMED or WOS) is not the same as doing it in this same journal, which allows high visibility for students, professors, or researchers from the first, second or third world.

The important thing at this point in life is that the world knows the reality in terms of research of Veterinary Medicine students, in this case and incidentally that they appear as the first author, something that is highly valued today.

2. Material and methods

Most of the published work is related to the veterinary sciences, almost always including veterinary medicine students as first authors, both in published works and in conference presentations (which we could talk about another day). The place has been since 1997 the Department of Animal Preventive Medicine of the Faculty of Veterinary Sciences (FAVET) of the University of Chile and thanks to the high sponsorship of research projects such as Fondecyt, others financed by FAVET or recently thanks to the support of the Fundación Wolf, Illinois, USA.

The subject of research has been the detection and/or characterization of pathogens that affect animal species and lately those considered small animals. These topics have been at the permanent service of students who finish their studies with us, that is, they finally achieve the title in Veterinary Medicine.

* Corresponding author: Carlos Navarro Venegas
Faculty of Veterinary and Livestock Sciences (FAVET), University of Chile, Santiago, Chile.

3. Results and discussion

All of the above is recorded in an *academic handbook*, where only *noble* works are included, understanding as those only those published in *noble* journals (<https://mu3-portafolio.uchile.cl/index#investigacion-publicaciones>) indicating at least 10 works (sorry, it must be entered with an institutional username and password) [15, 19, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52, 53, 54].

However, the rest of the works published in journals of lesser origin do not appear in the academic manual, as if they did not exist, despite having an associated doi. It does not contribute to the university ranking [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16, 17, 19, 20, 21, 22,23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29,30,31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43]. As a consolation I can offer enter to <https://scholar.google.com/citations?hl=en&user=X7SIH4YAAAAJ> and to detect if the above is true or not.

On the other hand, when reviewing the published works, there is a 35/52 (67%) in which the student appears as the first author, including the total number of published works, in which there are not necessarily students involved. If only the works that led to a degree report (33/34) are considered, this value reaches 97%.

Finally, it is enough to review the works published and visible on the Internet to verify whether or not there is an innate capacity to carry out this and other types of work and be an Associate Professor according to FAVET. *There is no evil that lasts 100 years.*

4. Conclusion

The existence of other sources of information such as Google Scholar, ICMJE, Crossref member, Researchgate, IFSIJS, QUALIS, SJIF, Index Copernicus, DRJI, CiteFactor, Research Bible and others, allows for international visibility and if the terminology persists over time (impact factor), I have no doubt that many of the journals indexed in these alternative sources will manage to reach Olympus.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

Infinite thanks to all the students who fulfilled their dreams with us and thanks to Fondecyt, FAVET and especially to Dr. Aron Mosnaim, from the Wolf Foundation, Illinois, USA.

References

- [1] Navarro; C.; Jara M.A. 2022. Design of primers in the Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR protocol. One introduction. Available in: <https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/mhsej/article/view/74/73>
- [2] Mora-Cornejo; A.; Navarro; C. 2022. Design of a protocol for the detection of parvovirus interspecies through Polymerase Chain Reaction. IJMRGE. Available in: <https://www.allmultidisciplinaryjournal.com/archivesarticle/2022.v3.i1.616.pdf>
- [3] Raggi; LA.; Jara ; MA; Navarro; C. 2022. One current viral threat to wildlife or in captivity. Open Access Research Journal of Biology and Pharmacy. Available in: <https://doi.org/10.53022/oarjbp.2022.4.2.0033>
- [4] Navarro; C; Céspedes; PF. 2022. Some details in the study of viruses that affect to small animals. GSC Advanced Research and Reviews (GSCARR). Available in: <https://gsconlinepress.com/journals/gscarr/sites/default/files/GSCARR-2022-0068.pdf>
- [5] Fuentes; A.; Jara; MA.; Navarro; C. 2022. Detection of ul37 gene from Canine Herpes Virus by Polymerase Chain Reaction. IJMRGE. Available in: <https://www.allmultidisciplinaryjournal.com/search?q=A-22-82&type=archives>
- [6] Vera; C; Jara; MA; Navarro; C. 2022. A preliminary studio for the F gen of Canine Distemper Virus as target for phylogenetic analysis. GSCARR. Available in: <https://gsconlinepress.com/journals/gscarr/sites/default/files/GSCARR-2022-0034.pdf>
- [7] Vargas; M.; Jara; MA.; Navarro; C. 2022. Use of primer design to detect the Glycoprotein C gene of Canine Herpes Virus by Polymerase Chain Reaction. ASVS. Available in: <https://actascientific.com/ASVS/pdf/ASVS-04-0337.pdf>

- [8] Navarro; C. 2022. One health or how to see the training of new veterinary doctors with the right eyes. IJFLSR. Available in: <https://frontiersrj.com/journals/ijflsr/sites/default/files/IJFLSR-2021-0049.pdf>
- [9] Carrasco; L.; Jara; MA; Navarro; C. 2022. Detection of the canine herpes virus glycoprotein B gene via Polymerase Chain Reaction. OARJMS. Available in: <https://doi.org/10.53022/oarjms.2022.3.1.0031>
- [10] Carreño; C.; Navarro; C.; Jara MA. 2021. Design of primers in the molecular detection of Feline Panleukopenia Virus. WJBPHS. Available in: <https://wjbphs.com/content/design-primers-molecular-detection-feline-panleukopenia-virus>
- [11] Navarro; C. 2021. Biosecurity in times of COVID19 or how to take it seriously. WJARR. 12(03); 560–562. Available in: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2021.12.3.0697>
- [12] Navarro; C. 2021. The virology in small animals or how to get out of complicated questions. IRJASET. Available in: <https://www.cirdjournal.com/index.php/irjaset/article/view/143>
- [13] Méndez-Valenzuela; VK.; Jara; M.A.; Navarro; C. 2021. Canine Distemper Virus: Multiple detection of the H and N genes by the Polymerase Chain Reaction associated with Reverse Transcriptase. CJVDS. Available in: <https://www.corpuspublishers.com/assets/articles/article-pdf-158.pdf>
- [14] Navarro; C. 2021. Multidisciplinary vision in the teaching of Veterinary Medicine. ASVS. Available in: <https://actascientific.com/ASVS/pdf/ASVS-03-0127.pdf>
- [15] Vergara-Wilson; V.; Hidalgo-Hermoso; H.; Sánchez; C.; Abarca; M.; Navarro; C.; Celis-Diez; S.; Soto-Guerrero; P.; Diaz-Ayala; N.; Zordan; M.; Cifuentes-Ramos; F.; Cabello-Stom; J. 2021. Canine Distemper Outbreak by Natural Infection in a Group of Vaccinated Maned Wolves in Captivity. Pathogens. Available in: <https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens10010051>
- [16] Zenteno; C.; Jara; MA; Navarro; C. 2020. Preliminary use of primers of Canine Herpes Virus gene ul37 in detection of Feline Herpes Virus by Polymerase Chain Reaction. AJCR. Available in: <https://www.cirdjournal.com/index.php/ajcr/article/view/293/282>
- [17] Navarro; C.; Cáceres. A.; Gaggero; A. 2020. Detection of Canine Parvovirus in Dogs by Means Polymerase Chain Reaction. AJBSR. Available in: <http://dx.doi.org/10.34297/AJBSR.2020.07.001219>
- [18] Cisternas; F.; Navarro; C.; Jara MA. 2020. Feline calicivirus. Molecular detection with primers design. ECVS. Available in: <https://www.econicon.com/ecve/pdf/ECVE-05-00260.pdf>
- [19] Hidalgo-Hermoso; E.; Cabello; J.; Vega; C.; Kroeger-Gómez; H.; Moreira-Arce; D.; Napolitano; C.; Navarro; C.; Sacristán; I.; Cevidanes; A.; Di Cataldo; S.; Dubovi; E.; Mathieu-Benson; C.; Millán; J. 2020. An eight-year survey for canine distemper virus indicates lack of exposure in the endangered Darwin's fox (*Lycalopex fulvipes*). J Wild Dis. Available in: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31833816/>
- [20] Correa;V.; Céspedes; PF.; Navarro; C. 2019. Promising use of Polymerase Chain Reaction Associated to Reverse Transcription for the Detection of the America-1 Lineage of Canine Distemper Virus. IJRSZ. Available in: <https://www.arcjournals.org/pdfs/ijrsz/v5-i1/4.pdf>
- [21] Mateo; F.; Céspedes; PF.; Navarro; C. 2019. The Phosphoprotein Gene from Canine Distemper Virus as Target in Viral Detection. IJZAB. Disponible <https://medwinpublishers.com/IZAB/the-phosphoprotein-gene-from-canine-distemper-virus-as-target-in-viral-detection.pdf>
- [22] Sepúlveda; C.; Jara; MA.; Navarro; C. 2019. Detección molecular del gen de la glicoproteína B del virus herpes felino. Vaccimonitor. Available in: <http://scielo.sld.cu/pdf/vac/v28n3/1025-0298-vac-28-03-103.pdf>
- [23] Navarro; C.; Muñoz; C.; Céspedes; P. 2019. The Nucleocapside Protein Gene As Excellent Target For Detection Of Canine Distemper Virus by Reverse Transcriptase-Polymerase Chain Reaction. Am J Biomed Sci & Res. Available in: <https://biomedgrid.com/pdf/AJBSR.MS.ID.000935.pdf>
- [24] Navarro; C.; Raggi; LA. 2019. Characterization of union sites for opioids in human lymphocyte Membranes. Am J Biomed Sci & Res. Available in: <https://biomedgrid.com/pdf/AJBSR.MS.ID.000803>
- [25] Bolívar; P.; Céspedes; P.; Navarro; C. 2019. Use of the Reverse Transcription-Polymerase Chain reaction for differential detection of two lineages of the canine distemper virus in Chile. IVS. Available in: <https://www.heighpubs.org/hvsr/pdf/ivs-aid1014.pdf>
- [26] Zuñiga; B.; Jara; MA.; Mosnaim; AD.; Navarro; C. 2019. Detection of Resistance mecA gene in Gram positive bacteria described as nosocomial. Am J Biomed Sci & Res. Available in: <https://biomedgrid.com/pdf/AJBSR.MS.ID.000831.pdf>

- [27] Sánchez; P.; Borie; C.; Navarro; C. 2019. Diagnosis of Salmonella Enteritidis in tissues and intestinal content of experimentally infected chickens in Chile by Polymerase Chain Reaction. IJMRAS. Available in: <https://ijmras.com/index.php/IJMRAS/article/view/50/46>
- [28] Obreque; B.; Jara; Ma.; Raggi. LA.; Navarro; C. 2019. Positive Controls in the Detection of Genes of Resistance in Bacteria of Veterinary Interest. J Vet Sci Animal Welf. Available in: <https://www.ommegaonline.org/article-details/Positive-controls-in-the-detection-of-genes-of-resistance-to-tetracyclines-in-bacteria-of-veterinary-interest/2452>
- [29] Valenzuela-Parra; Jara; MA.; Raggi; LA.; Navarro; C. 2018. Use of Multiplex Polymerase Chain Reaction in detection of Canine Herpes Virus glycoprotein B gene. IOSR Journal of Agriculture and Veterinary Science (IOSRJAVS). Available in: <https://www.iosrjournals.org/iosr-javs/papers/Vol11-issue11/Version-2/E1111023640.pdf>
- [30] Yáñez; D.; Jara; MA.; Navarro; C. 2018. Detection of BlaTEM resistance gene in bacteria described as nosocomial. GJFSR. Available in: [https://globaljournals.org/GJSFR_Volume18/E-journal_GJSFR_\(D\)_Vol_18_Issue_7.pdf](https://globaljournals.org/GJSFR_Volume18/E-journal_GJSFR_(D)_Vol_18_Issue_7.pdf)
- [31] Tamayo; N.; Jara; MA.; Navarro; C. 2018. Molecular diagnosis of Bordetella spp. by means the semi-nested Polymerase Chain Reaction. GJFSR. Available in: [https://globaljournals.org/GJSFR_Volume18/E-Journal_GJSFR_\(D\)_Vol_18_Issue_7.pdf](https://globaljournals.org/GJSFR_Volume18/E-Journal_GJSFR_(D)_Vol_18_Issue_7.pdf)
- [32] Bravo; J.; Navarro; C. 2018. Use of Polymerase Chain Reaction and Endonuclease restriction BclI for differential Lepstospira interrogans detection. IJSR. Available in <https://www.ijsr.net/archive/v7i8/ART2019434.pdf>
- [33] Abarca; MJ.; Hidalgo; E.; Raggi; LA.; Navarro; C. 2018. Genotypic evidence of infection by Canine Distemper Virus in maned Wolf from a zoological collection. IJSR. Available in: <https://www.ijser.org/researchpaper/Genotypic-evidence-of-infection-by-Canine-Distemper-Virus-in-maned-wolf-from-a-zoological-collection-in-Chile.pdf>
- [34] Pincheira; D.; Céspedes; P.; Pizarro; J.; Navarro; C. 2018. Molecular detection of Canine Distemper Virus through the use of the Large Polymerase Gene. EASJALS. Available in: https://www.easpublisher.com/media/articles/EASJALS_12_39-43_c.pdf
- [35] Jara; P.; Céspedes; P.; Navarro; C. 2018. Canine Distemper Virus detection based in Hemagglutinine gen as target in reverse transcriptase-Polymerase Chain reaction. IVS. Available in: <https://www.heighpubs.org/hvsr/pdf/ivs-aid1012.pdf>
- [36] Macías; P.; Navarro; C. 2018. Molecular detection of Feline Herpesvirus by means Polymerase Chain Reaction. JDVS. Available in: <https://juniperpublishers.com/jdvs/JDVS.MS.ID.555736.php>
- [37] Gallegos; M.; Céspedes; P.; Pizarro; J.; Navarro; C. 2018. Is the M gene of Canine Distemper virus a eligible target for detection? EASJALS Available in: https://www.easpublisher.com/media/articles/EASJALS_11_22-32_c.pdf
- [38] Fuentes; A.; Carrasco; L.; Vargas; M.; Valenzuela-Parra; C.; Céspedes; P.; Navarro; C. 2018. Genomic characterization of Canine Herpes Virus; the etiological agent of fatal hemorrhagic disease in newborn puppies. EMS. Available in: <https://www.emspublishers.org/Articles/Genomic-Characterization-of-Canine-Herpes-Virus-the-Etiological-Agent-of-Fatal-Hemorrhagic-Disease-in-Newborn-Puppies-003.pdf>
- [39] Lobos; C.; Martínez; MA.; Navarro; C. 2018. Detection of Mycoplasma spp. in Cell Cultures by genus-Specific Polymerase Chain Reaction Protocol. JVSMD. Available in: https://www.scitechnol.com/peer-review/detection-of-mycoplasma-spp-in-cell-cultures-by-genusspecific-polymerase-chain-reaction-protocol-vA1W.php?article_id=7653
- [40] Lorca; V.; Borie; C.; Navarro; C. 2018. Differential detection of Brucella canis by means a conventional Polymerase Chain Reaction. Vet Sci Med. Available in: <http://sciaeon.org/articles/Differential-Detection-of-Brucella-Canis-by-Means-a-Conventional-Polymerase-Chain-Reaction.pdf>
- [41] Salas; V.; Pizarro; J.; Navarro; C. 2018. Phylogenetic analysis of canine distemper virus detected in Chile. IJCR. Available in: <https://www.journalcra.com/sites/default/files/issue-pdf/31909.pdf>
- [42] Céspedes; P.; Jara; MA.; Navarro; C. 2018. Molecular detection of resistance genes to biocides in Nosocomial bacteria. Vet Sci Med. Available in: <http://sciaeon.org/articles/Detection-of-Resistance-Genes-to-Biocides-in-Bacteria-Nosocomiales-by-Means-the-Chain-Reaction-of-the-Polymerase.pdf>
- [43] Saldías L.; Navarro; C. 2018. Determination of Permissive Cellular Lines to the Canine Herpes Virus; by Visualization of the Cytopathic Effect. Biomed J Sci & Tech Res. Available in: <https://biomedres.us/fulltexts/BJSTR.MS.ID.002028.php>

- [44] Galarce; N.; Escobar; B.; Rojas; Navarro; C.; Turra; G.; Robeson; J.; Borie; C. 2016. Application of avirulent bacteriophage cocktail leads to reduction of *Salmonella enterica* serovar Enteritidis counts in processed meat products. *Biocontrol; Science and Tech* 4: 463-475. Abstract Available in: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/09583157.2015.1125447>
- [45] Jorquera; D.; Navarro; C.; Rojas; V.; Turra; G.; Robeson; J.; Borie; C. 2015. The use of a bacteriophage cocktail as a biocontrol measure to reduce *Salmonella enterica* serovar Enteritidis contamination in ground meat and goat cheese. *Biocontrol Science and Technology* 25:970-974. Abstract Available in: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/09583157.2015.1018815?src=recsys>
- [46] Cepeda; CP.; Navarro; C.; Celedon; MO. 2011. Prospección serológica del virus parainfluenza en camélidos sudamericanos en Chile. *Arch Med Vet.* Available in: <https://scielo.conicyt.cl/pdf/amv/v43n2/art11.pdf>
- [47] Céspedes; P.; Cruz; C.; Navarro; C. 2010. Modulación de la respuesta inmune durante la infección por Virus Distemper Canino: implicancias terapéuticas y en el desarrollo de vacunas. *Arch Med Vet.* Available in: <https://scielo.conicyt.cl/pdf/amv/v42n2/art03.pdf>
- [48] Borie; C.; Sánchez; M.; Navarro; C.; Ramírez; S.; Morales; M.; Retamales; J.; Robeson; J. 2009. Aerosol Spray Treatment with Bacteriophage and Competitive Exclusion Reduce *Salmonella* Enteritidis Infection in Chickens. *Avian Diseases* 53: 250-254. Abstract Available in: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/19630232>
- [49] Borie; C.; Albala; I.; Sanchez; P.; Sánchez; M.; Ramírez; S.; Navarro; C.; Morales; M.; Retamales; J.; Robeson. 2008. Bacteriophage treatment reduce *Salmonella* colonization in infected chickens. *J. Avian diseases* 5: 64-67. Abstract Available in: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/18459298>
- [50] Navarro; C.; Celedón; M.; Pizarro; J.; Gaggero; A. 2005. Virus herpes canino en Chile: Propiedades biológicas. *Arch Med Vet.* Available in: https://scielo.conicyt.cl/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S0301-732X2005000200007
- [51] Pizarro-Lucero; J.; Celedón; M. O.; Navarro; C.; Ortega; R.; González; D. 2005. Identification of a pestivirus isolated from free-ranging pudu (*Pudu puda*) in Chile. *Vet. Rec.* 157: 292-294. Available in: <https://veterinaryrecord.bmj.com/content/157/10/292.long>
- [52] Navarro; C.; Celedón; Mo.; Pizarro; J. 2003. Detección de virus herpes canino tipo 1 en Chile. *Arch Med Vet.* Available in: https://scielo.conicyt.cl/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S0301-732X2003000200010
- [53] Celedón; M.; Sandoval; M.; Droguett; J.; Calfio; R.; Pizarro; J.; Navarro; C. 2001. Survey for antibodies to pestivirus and herpesvirus in sheep; goats; alpacas (*Lama pacos*); llamas (*Lama glama*); guanacos (*Lama guanicoe*) and vicuna (*Vicugna vicugna*) from Chile. *Arch Med Vet.* Available in: <http://revistas.uach.cl/html/amv/v33n2/body/art05.html>
- [54] Puente; J.; Maturana; P.; Miranda; D.; Navarro; C.; Wolf; ME.; Mosnaim; AD. 1992. Enhancement of human natural killer cell activity by opioid peptides: similar response to methionine-enkephalin and beta-endorphin. *Brain Behav Immun.* 6: 32-39. Available in: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/088915919290057U?via%3Dihub>